

IMPACT DAMAGE IN COMPOSITES -
DEVELOPMENT, CONSEQUENCES AND PREVENTION

G Dorey
Royal Aircraft Establishment
Farnborough, Hampshire GU14 6TD
UK

ABSTRACT

The various fracture modes of composite materials affect the impact behaviour of fibrous laminates and have important implications for the design of composite structures.

The fracture characteristics of fibrous composites are reviewed briefly and it is shown how toughness depends on preferential splitting parallel to the fibres. The extent of this splitting depends on the properties of the fibres and of the matrix, on the interfacial bond strength, and on interactions between the plies in the laminate. Under impact loading, the damage produced shows similar trends with material properties, but also depends on the velocity, energy and properties of the impacting projectile, and in particular on the dynamic response of the composite specimen. Testing at different velocities can produce stain-rate effects or changes in failure mode, and this will affect the design of standard impact tests.

The various types of impact damage affect different mechanical properties, mainly producing significant reductions in static strengths but also possibly affecting fatigue properties and environmental effects. For structural applications, the design requirements should be related to the possible incidence of impact damage and its effects on performance. Improvements in impact performance are being made through changes to the basic materials, through combining them in hybrid forms and through modifications in structural designs.

INTRODUCTION

Advanced composite materials for aerospace applications usually comprise high performance fibres in an appropriate matrix, with the fibres carefully arranged to carry the applied loads and packed in with volume fractions of about 60%. Stress-strain curves of typical reinforcing fibres are shown in Fig 1. Carbon, boron and aramid fibres have

high specific stiffnesses and are useful for lightweight air control surfaces, where maintaining the shape under aerodynamic loads is required. They also have high specific strengths and are finding increasing numbers of applications in primary load bearing structures. Glass fibres are strong but are more compliant and are damage tolerant, finding useful applications in helicopters. Aramid fibres have high specific strengths and, because of their tendency to defibrillate, are particularly tenuous in bending and are used widely in lightweight armour.

Figure 1. Stress-strain curves for typical reinforcing fibres used in advanced composite materials.

The matrix material supports the fibres and has usually been a thermosetting resin, such as an epoxy or for higher temperatures a polyimide, although thermoplastics are also finding uses. The use of such resins allows the moulding of complex shapes with fewer parts and less joining operations, resulting in reductions in the cost of manufacture. Specific designs can trade efficiency in performance for cost of manufacture and/or maintenance.

Although glass and aramid fibres are used for their damage tolerance, carbon fibre composites (CFRP) can be susceptible to impact damage [1-3] and can cause design limits to be set below 0.5% strain, less than one third of the fibre failure strain. A better understanding

of the micro mechanics of the failure processes should increase confidence in the performance of carbon fibre composites and allow more efficient use of the fibre strength. In addition, recent improvements in both the fibre and matrix properties have further increased the useful performance of carbon fibre composites and will widen the range of possible applications. This paper attempts to review the impact behaviour of advanced composite materials, how it is affected by material properties and recent trends in material development.

FRACTURE CHARACTERISTICS

Unidirectional fibre composites have high strength and stiffness, imparted by the fibres, in the fibre direction or longitudinal direction. In the transverse direction the strength is much lower (about one thirtieth of the longitudinal strength). In a notched composite, subjected to a longitudinal tensile stress, there is a complex stress field near the notch tip. The greatest stress concentration is at the notch tip in the longitudinal stress, which is in the direction of maximum strength parallel to the fibres. However smaller local stresses, such as shear stresses at the notch tip or transverse tensile stresses ahead of the notch, can exceed the low transverse strengths and cause splitting parallel to the fibres, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Splits parallel to the fibres in a unidirectional composite due to local stresses, (a) shear, (b) transverse tension.

This splitting effectively blunts the notch and removes the stress concentration at the notch tip, and thus unidirectional composites are

3.4

usually "notch insensitive". The splitting parallel to the fibres is a relatively low energy fracture process. For carbon fibre/epoxy composites the initial fracture energy is about 100 J/m^2 , similar to that for unreinforced epoxy resins, but as the split progresses misaligned fibres form a tied zone behind the crack front and the fracture energy can increase as these fibres have to be broken for the crack to advance. Fracture across the fibres requires much more energy; of the order of 50 to 100 kJ/m^2 depending on the amount of associated splitting.

Multidirectional laminates are usually notch sensitive, as illustrated for CFRP under tensile loading in Figure 3. The failure stress is significantly below the line expected from the net section strength for a notch insensitive material. In this particular laminate, sharp notches were found to be more detrimental than round holes, but for smaller notches and tougher materials this distinction gets less marked. However the failure stresses are generally greater than would be expected for brittle materials.

Figure 3. The notch sensitivity of a $[0,90,0\pm 45,0]_s$ CFRP laminate under tensile loading.

As with the unidirectional composites, the complex stresses near the notch tip cause splitting parallel to the fibres within the individual plies, and delamination occurs between the plies, forming a damage zone at the notch tip [4], as shown in Figure 4. This damage zone absorbs energy,

increasing the fracture energy, but most important are the splits parallel to the longitudinal 0 degree fibres because they are the most effective in blunting the notch and reducing the stress concentration in the 0 degree fibres which carry most of the load. The size of this damage zone depends on fibre, matrix and interface properties but also on ply thicknesses and on proportions of plies in the various directions [5].

Figure 4. Damage zones formed at notch tips in CFRP laminates under tensile loading, observed by a laser moiré method, (a) $[\pm 45, 0]_S$, (b) $[0, \pm 45]_S$, (after reference 4).

Similar crack blunting mechanisms have been observed under compression loading [6,7], even though failure is usually associated with some fibre buckling instability, as shown in Figure 5. Under room temperature dry conditions, final failure often occurs by in-plane shear buckling of the 0 degree fibres along a 45 degree direction associated with a shear crack in the 45 degree ply, with a net section stress similar to that for unnotched material. However under hot/wet conditions the shear modulus of the resin can be reduced, so that there is less resistance to fibre buckling, and at relatively low loads the local stresses can precipitate an out-of-plane shear failure in the 0 degree fibres along a 90 degree direction.

Figure 5. Changes in damage zones and failure modes with environmental conditions in a notched (0,±45) CFRP laminate, under compressive loading (after reference 7).

FIBRE/MATRIX INTERFACE

The reinforcement efficiency of a fibre matrix system, and the degree to which the material splits during failure processes, depends on the adhesion at the fibre/matrix interface. The only reason that brittle fibres in a brittle matrix can have any appreciable toughness at all, is that cracks get diverted up the fibre/matrix interface, like green-stick fractures observed with wood and bone. If there is too weak a fibre/matrix bond, the material will not support loads in shear or compression; too strong a bond and the material will be brittle. This can be affected by the fibre structure, the fibre surface condition, the size or surface finish, and the matrix structure both at the interface and away from the interface.

Glass fibres have a silane finish applied, to both protect the glass surface from degradation and to increase the adhesion to resin matrices. Polymeric fibres can have their surfaces etched to increase adhesion, but high modulus polymer fibres such as aramid fibres tend to defibrillate at internal interfaces so there is a limit to which the fibre/matrix bond strength is effective. In both glass fibre and aramid fibre composite

laminates the failure processes are dominated by the relatively weak interfaces.

In carbon fibre composites the interface bond strength is increased by means of an oxidative treatment to the surface of the carbon fibres [8]. This increased bond strength can be seen in Figure 6, where the interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) increased with fibre surface treatment up to a certain value; for greater levels of surface treatment the ILSS remained reasonably constant and this may be because shear failures were occurring in the resin rather than at the interface.

Figure 6. The effect of carbon fibre surface treatment and hence fibre/matrix bond strength on the interlaminar shear strength of a unidirectional CFRP composite and on the notch sensitivity of a $0_2, +45_2, -45_2, 0_2]_S$ CFRP laminate.

Other properties of unidirectional CFRP such as transverse tensile strength, longitudinal compression strength and flexural strength, showed similar trends. Multidirectional laminates behaved differently and the notched tensile strength continued to decrease, as the fibre surface treatment was increased, even in the range where the ILSS was not changing. The fibre surface treatment clearly affects the intraply splitting at the notch tip and the formation of the damage zones.

The mechanisms of the bonding between carbon fibres and resin matrices are still receiving much attention with attempts to correlate the surface topography and chemical activity with composite failure modes and mechanical properties. The important technological point is that, unlike glass or aramid fibre composites, carbon fibre composites can have too great a bond strength between the fibre and the resin, resulting in brittle materials. The fibre surface treatment has to be optimised for the fibre/resin system and it has to be carefully controlled.

IMPACT DAMAGE

Traditionally, impact tests such as Izod and Charpy tests have been used to indicate the impact toughness of isotropic materials, and they have yielded useful information on notch effects and brittle-tough transition temperatures. However, because of the complexity of composite failure processes, these tests are only of limited value with composite materials and they give no indication of residual properties after impact. Dropweight tests (simulating dropped tools) and ballistic tests (simulating runway stones) have proved more useful.

The various forms of impact damage observed are shown schematically in Figure 7, together with expressions for the energy needed to cause them, typical values for 2mm thick CFRP and the area of damage caused. It can be seen, from the effects of geometry, that delaminations are more likely with short spans, thick laminates or laminates with low inter-laminar shear strength. Flexural failures are more likely with large spans or thin skins. Penetration is most likely for small projectiles moving at a sufficiently high velocity that the laminate cannot respond quickly enough in flexure and high stresses are generated closer to the point of impact.

In dropweight tests, the supports may be instrumented with strain gauges to give a load-time trace during the impact, as illustrated in Figure 8. The area under this trace is the impulse between the projectile and the specimen and is equal to the change in momentum of the projectile. When there was no failure, the peak load occurred when the projectile came to rest, its kinetic energy being converted into elastic strain energy within the composite specimen, and the second half of the curve corresponds to the projectile rebounding. When a flexural failure occurred the

Figure 7. The primary failure modes of composite laminates under impact loading, the elastic strain energy at the point of failure and typical values of threshold energy and corresponding areas of damage for CFRP; w , l and t are the width, unsupported length and thickness of the specimen, d is the diameter of the ball, τ is the ILSS, σ is the flexural strength, E is the flexural modulus, and γ is the fracture energy.

projectile did not rebound, the elastic strain energy causing damage to the composite. The shear failure resulted in a change of stiffness of the laminate, but it could still carry load and the projectile rebounded but with a reduced momentum. With the circular support, the specimen was supported all round its edge, unlike the first three cases with just end supports. This made the specimen stiffer and critical loads were reached sooner and for less energy. The fracture process continued longer at high loads because cracks were being driven into regions of lower stress nearer the support, and the low stored elastic energy meant that further input of energy was required from the projectile to continue the fracture process.

Increasing use is being made of instrumented impact testing. This is usually done on dropweight machines or pendulum impact machines, where the striker is instrumented to measure the applied load. The impacting energy is usually much greater than that needed to break or penetrate the

Figure 8. Load time traces during dropweight impact on CFRP laminates, using either end supports or circular supports.

specimen and displacement can usually be related to time. However some machines have independent means of measuring displacement. Thus traces of load-displacement can be obtained and these can be converted to give energy-displacement traces, so that features such as peak load and absorbed energy can be related to fracture processes occurring in the material. An example is shown in Figure 9 for a sandwich panel comprising aramid skins on a nomex honeycomb core [9]. The peak loads associated with the penetration of the two skins can be clearly distinguished.

Also of interest in impact testing are effects due to strain rate. Tensile tests on various CFRP laminates, $[08]$, $[0,90,0,\pm 45,0]_s$ plain and notched and $[(\pm 45)_3]_s$ plain and notched, over a range of strain rate from 0.001/s to 100/s, showed no effect on failure stress. This has been confirmed [10] at higher strain rates using a Hopkinson bar technique as shown in Figure 10. Although the CFRP showed no significant strain rate effect up to over 1000/s, the glass fibre composite specimens showed a significant increase in failure strain. Similar effects have been seen when comparing strain rates used in static and fatigue tests; composites using carbon fibres or aramid fibres showed no effect of strain rate whereas GRP did show an increase in failure load with increasing strain

Figure 9. Load-deflection and energy-deflection traces during drop-weight impact on an aramid faced sandwich panel (after reference 9).

rate. Although strain rate may have little effect in any given failure mode, projectiles travelling at different velocities can cause the failure mode to change because of the dynamic response of the specimen.

If the impact results in visible damage, this can be clearly seen on inspection and if it occurred on a composite structure the appropriate remedial action could be taken. Delaminations however are not visible even though there may be significant internal damage to the laminate as shown in Figure 11. The damage is often worse towards the back of the laminate, which makes detection more difficult. Delaminations can be detected by ultrasonic techniques. C-scans give a silhouette of the damaged areas and A or B-scans give information on the depth of the damage, but it is difficult to inspect large complex structures in this way. Useful information on the damage can also be obtained using X-rays but this requires the use of a radio opaque dye to penetrate the damaged region.

Figure 10. Effect of strain rate on the impact strain capability of various glass fibre and carbon fibre composites (after reference 10).

Figure 11. Multiple delaminations in a $[(0_2, \pm 45)_2]_S$ CFRP laminate caused by dropweight impact.

Thicker laminates cannot always respond by flexing and impact causes front surface damage, rather like erosion damage by small particles.

However if the projectile has sufficient energy to penetrate the thick laminate, then it may result in front face erosion for approximately half the thickness, and then delamination and the usual flexural response can occur in the rear half of the laminate [11], as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Impact damage in a 64 ply CFRP laminate caused by ballistic impact (after reference 11).

Similar work has been done on composite structures incorporating features such as stiffeners. It was found that impact in the middle of the bay required 30 to 50 Joules of energy to cause barely visible impact damage (BVID), because of the relatively large volume of material that was being deformed, whereas near a stiffener where the structure was stiffer only a few Joules were needed. Also the stiffeners altered the local response of the panel so that damage was sometimes observed to one side of the point of impact or even away from the point of impact. Clearly the more complex the impact conditions the more closely must the test condition simulate the practical situation.

RESIDUAL STRENGTH AFTER IMPACT

The different forms of impact damage affect the various laminate strengths to different degrees, and for this reason it is difficult to have a single impact parameter to describe the "impact resistance". Delamination causes reductions in interlaminar shear strength (Figure 13) and the residual ILSS can be predicted from the area of delamination using

a fracture mechanics model and an interlaminar fracture toughness [12]. The damage observed for both dropweight and ballgun impact depended on the energy of the projectile, even though the velocities and momenta were very different.

Figure 13. Effect of impact damage on the residual ILSS of a $[(0,90)_3]_S$ CFRP laminate.

Larger spans resulted in flexural damage, with reductions in flexural and tensile strength, as illustrated in Figure 14. Again the reductions in strength occurred at similar incident energies for both the dropweight and ballgun impact, although in this case the threshold energy for damage was significantly higher than for the smaller span used for the residual shear strength measurements. For the ballgun impact the maximum amount of damage was done at incident energies just sufficient to cause penetration by the 6 mm ball. At higher velocities, the ball penetrated the laminate relatively cleanly, losing little energy, causing little cracking away from the hole and resulting in smaller reductions in strength.

The threshold energy for flexural failures can be affected by the material properties and the ply stacking sequence, as shown in Figure 15. Increasing the resin toughness increased the flexural strength (σ), and therefore increased the energy ($C\sigma^2/E$), needed to cause failure. Putting the 45 degree plies on the outside reduced the flexural strength but it also reduced the flexural modulus (E), so that the threshold energy ($C\sigma^2/E$) was increased.

Figure 14. Effect of impact damage on the residual tensile strength of a $[(0,90)_3]_S$ CFRP laminate. The dashed line represents penetration by the ball.

Figure 15. Effect of resin toughness and ply stacking sequence on the threshold dropweight energy for flexural failure in CFRP laminates, $\longrightarrow [(\pm 45)_2, 0_4]_S$, $- - - [0_2 +45_2, -45_2, 0_2]_S$.

One of the main energy absorbing mechanisms in composite materials is the strain energy to failure of the fibres, or the area under the fibre stress-strain curve shown in Figure 1. Lower modulus fibres such as glass fibres and aramid fibres have a larger energy absorbing capacity. It is therefore possible to make hybrid laminates incorporating glass or aramid fibres to improve the impact resistance of CFRP. It is preferable to put the glass or aramid fibres on the surface [12] because the strains are greater there in flexure, and these surface plies can prevent fretting of the carbon fibres or fibre breakout on the back face.

Residual compression strength after impact is particularly important. In order to have a sufficiently large gauge section to accommodate the damage it is necessary to have anti-buckling guides to support the specimen, but these should not prevent local instabilities in the damaged region. Delaminations, under in-plane compression loading, tend to grow transverse to the applied load because this gives the greatest increase in compliance or the greatest strain energy release rate. Typical results are shown in Figure 16. There was a marked reduction in compression strength for delamination damage (up to 2 J), that had little effect on tensile strength. The tensile strength did not decrease until there was significant fibre damage. Lower values of fibre surface treatment gave tougher laminates in tension especially in the region of fibre damage, as explained for notches in the earlier section on fibre/matrix interface. But the residual compression strengths were lower with less fibre surface treatment, because of larger areas of delamination and less resistance to delamination growth. Some improvements can be made by the judicious use of stitching through the thickness of the laminate before moulding, to reduce the incidence and growth of delamination.

A factor that might affect the damage and hence the residual strength is the static load that a component is carrying when it is impacted. It might be expected to be less capable of deforming elastically under impact and fail for a lower incident impact energy. Figure 17 shows that in tension there was a slight reduction in residual strength with preload, especially at intermediate impact energies where the maximum damage was done, but the main effect was a complete failure on impact if the tensile preload exceeded the expected residual tensile strength.

Figure 16. Effect of fibre surface treatment on the residual tensile and compressive strengths of $[(0_2, \pm 45)_2]_S$ CFRP laminates after dropweight impact.

Figure 17. Effect of tensile preload on the residual tensile strength of a $[0,90,0, \pm 45, 0]_S$ CFRP laminate.

Similar results have been obtained with compression preloads[13], as shown in Figure 18. At high incident energies the transition from

no-failure to failure-on-impact coincided with the residual strength for specimens that had not failed on impact. At intermediate incident energies the residual strengths were significantly higher than this transition preload.

Figure 18. Effect of compressive preload or prestrain on the impact behaviour of a $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2, \pm 45, 0, 90]_{2s}$ CFRP laminate (after reference 13).

Of practical concern for service structures is the possible growth of small sub-critical areas of delamination under fatigue loading, to the point of becoming critical. Figure 19 shows S-N curves, for fully reversed cyclic loading of undamaged CFRP laminates and laminates containing delamination. It can be seen that the damage significantly reduced the static and low cycle fatigue strengths but the S-N curve for the damaged laminate was very flat and after one million cycles the fatigue strengths of the damaged and undamaged specimens were similar. It seems that loads that are not great enough to cause unstable damage growth and static failure are not likely to cause damage growth under fatigue loading. This has been found also with machined notches in CFRP

laminates made from woven and non-woven plies [14]. The low cycle fatigue strengths were reduced significantly by the notches but not affected much by the weave, whereas the long life fatigue strength was not affected much by the notches but was significantly lower in the woven material, because the cross-over points in the weave were initiation points for fatigue damage throughout the material. If design limits are set to take care of impact damage and machined notches then it seems that fatigue will not be a problem.

Figure 19. Post impact fatigue, under fully reversed cyclic loading, of damaged and undamaged $[0,90,0,\pm 45,0]_s$ CFRP laminates.

There is still a need to be able to predict the static strengths for notched laminates under tensile, compressive or shear loading and for delaminated laminates under compressive or shear loading. If damage could be reduced to an idealised notch and/or delamination then it might be possible to relate these to local stress fields in a realistic structure and therefore be able to predict structural failure loads.

THERMOSETTING AND THERMOPLASTIC MATRICES

Most of the applications for CFRP have used epoxy resin matrices and in some instances polyimides for higher temperature capability.

Thermoplastics offer certain advantages such as toughness and short moulding times, but their environmental resistance has been relatively poor. However poly-ether-ether-ketone (PEEK) is a semi-crystalline thermoplastic that is little affected by solvents and has a high melting point. It therefore has attractions as a matrix for CFRP.

Comparisons between carbon fibre/PEEK and carbon fibre/epoxy composites [15], showed that fibre dominated properties were similar, there being good translation of fibre properties to the carbon fibre/PEEK composites. However the shear modulus of the PEEK was lower than that of the epoxy, resulting in slightly lower compression strengths in the carbon fibre/PEEK. The PEEK matrix was tougher than epoxy resins and it showed some ability to flow under shear stresses. Thus it did not give a shear failure under three point bend, and interlaminar fracture toughness measurements gave values significantly higher than for carbon fibre/epoxy laminates. The increased toughness and shear strain capabilities resulted in much greater strains in tension tests on (± 45) laminates: there were as many incipient cracks, indicating that the interface bond strength was similar, but these did not readily grow into resin cracks and delaminations.

On impact at low energies, there was an indentation on the front face with associated radial compression cracks perpendicular to the fibres in the surface ply. Sections through these compression lines showed them to be compression failures with characteristic shear bands. Ultrasonic C-scans and X-rays of the impacted laminates showed less delamination with carbon fibre/PEEK and less fibre damage at the point of impact, but there was some 0 degree splitting not seen with epoxy matrices. It could be that the fibre/matrix bond could still fail in transverse tension, but that this did not cause the interlaminar shear cracking as with epoxies and the stress was relieved by transverse tensile cracks within the plies. Plots of delaminated areas against impact energy [15] showed that with carbon fibre/epoxy the delamination could extend a considerable distance, but that with carbon fibre/PEEK the damage was confined near the point of impact. Figure 20 shows polished cross sections through the point of impact for an incident energy of 7 Joules. With the PEEK matrix, there were fewer delaminations through the thickness and they were restricted in extent, whereas the laminate with the epoxy matrix showed delamination

at many more interfaces and they extended much further. The carbon fibre/PEEK cross section shows the front face indentation and the compression cracking.

Figure 20. Schematics of internal damage caused by dropweight impact of 7 Joules energy on $[\pm 45, 0_3, \pm 45, 0_2]_S$ laminates of carbon fibre/PEEK and carbon fibre/epoxy.

Because of the restriction of damage and the 0 degree splitting which tended to blunt any cracks produced by impact, the residual tensile strengths were greater for the carbon fibre/PEEK laminates [16]. In compression too, residual strengths were significantly greater in carbon fibre/PEEK because of the reduced damage and the greater resistance to damage growth. The greater residual compression strengths after impact, combined with the damage being visible on the front face at lower impact energies, give carbon fibre/PEEK a potential for raising design stresses when they are associated with BVID.

IMPROVED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Advanced composite materials are still relatively young and improvements are continually being made. By removing strength limiting flaws,

carbon fibre strengths have been increased significantly over the past few years. The manufacturers have produced two main classes of high strength carbon fibre, as shown in Figure 21. High strain carbon fibres have been produced by keeping the modulus the same and increasing the strength to about 5 GPa and the strain approaching 2%. Intermediate modulus fibres have maintained similar working strains but have increased the strength to about 5 GPa. In either case the strain energy to failure of the fibres has increased and this should restrict the damage and improve the impact performance.

Figure 21. Improvements in the strengths of carbon fibres.

Resin matrices are also being improved and significant increases can be made in the interlaminar fracture toughness. But this has usually been at the expense of hot/wet compression strength. With toughened epoxy matrices, the areas of delamination on impact are reduced but the residual tensile strengths may be no greater because the restriction of crack blunting mechanisms increases the notch sensitivity. However the residual compression strengths are significantly better with toughened epoxy matrices, and critical strains for the impact of compression loaded laminates are significantly greater [13], as shown in Figure 22. The moduli of the toughened resins [13] were slightly lower but the tensile

strains to failure had been increased from about 2% for the standard epoxy to about 6% for the toughened resins. The toughened laminates were able to withstand "standard" impacts when preloaded in compression to a strain of 0.5%, whereas the standard epoxy system could not, although Figure 22 shows that the selection of a "standard" impact could be misleading and one really needs a range of impact energies.

Figure 22. Effect of ballistic impact on the critical compression strain for preloaded CFRP laminates, 1 with a standard epoxy matrix and 2 and 3 with toughened matrices (after reference 13).

The toughened matrix systems, both thermoplastic [15,16] and thermoset [13], tend to produce compression failure modes comprising fibre or ply buckling instabilities, rather than the usual delamination growth, associated with compression failures of impact damaged CFRP laminates, as shown in Figure 23. These changes in failure mode need to be carefully considered in case apparent improvements in some properties produce degradations in others.

It is becoming evident that the requirements for composite components for civil aircraft and for military aircraft are diverging. Civil aircraft require hot/wet compression strength at 90°C and impact resistance,

Figure 23. Failure modes associated with the impact of compression loaded CFRP laminates (after reference 13).

usually measured by compressive performance after impact, as shown in Figure 24. For military aircraft the hot/wet compression strength has to be demonstrated at about 130°C. Higher T_g epoxies and bismaleimides are being developed for this but they tend to be less tough and could have impact problems.

In summary, the present generation of carbon fibre composites are being severely limited by poor impact resistance and poor hot/wet compression strengths. This makes design limits low compared with the materials capability (Figure 25), but significant mass savings can still be made. Improved understanding of the failure processes might improve the ratio of design stress to material strength, but greater advances are likely to come from material developments and improvements, and imaginative combinations of materials in hybrid structures.

Figure 24. The development of improved CFRP materials combining critical properties.

Figure 25. Potential improvements in design allowables for advanced composite components.

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